

Search for New Oral Hypoglycemic Agents. Part I. Synthesis of Some New Substituted Thioureas

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Several substituted thioureas have been prepared for testing their hypoglycemic activity.

Although the emergence of chemicals like Synthalin (Frank *et al.*, *Klin. Wochr.*, 1926, 5, 2100), phenylethylformamidinyliminourea hydrochloride (Pcmerauze *et al.*, *Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol.*, 1957, 95, 193), carbutamide and tolbutamide (Franke and Fuchs, *Deutsh. med. Woch.*, 1955, 80, 1449; Achelis and Hardebeck, *ibid.*, 1955, 80, 1455), and 5-propyl¹-2-*p*-aminobenzenesulphanilamide-1,3,4-thiadiazole (Janbon *et al.*, *Montpellier*, 1942, 21-22, 469) undoubtedly points to the possibility of a positive chemotherapeutic approach to the problem of diabetes, a really potent antidiabetic agent remains yet to be discovered. Various theories put forward from time to time have so far not offered any definite clue as to the mode of action of hypoglycemic agents and in the present state of our knowledge it is difficult to pin-point an attack on this complex syndrome condition and to build effective antidiabetic compounds on a specific rationale. It can be noted, however, that most of the active antidiabetic compounds are built round a guanidine (e.g., synthaline and phenylethylformamidinyliminourea hydrochloride), a urea (e.g., carbutamide, tolbutamide, and chlorpropamide), or a thiourea moiety [e.g., 5-propyl¹-2-*p*-aminobenzenesulphanilamide-1,3,4-thiadiazole (I: R = Pr¹) and 5-butyl¹-2-aminobenzenesulphonamide-1,3,4-thiadiazole (I: R = Buⁿ)].

(I)

In view of the above considerations several substituted thiourea derivatives have been prepared (a) by condensation of phenyl isothiocyanate with γ -diethylaminopropyl¹amine, γ -piperidino-propyl¹amine, γ -morpholinopropyl¹amine, *p*-aminoacetanilide, *p*-aminoacetophenone, 3,5-dibromo-4-hydroxyaniline, sulphanilamide, sulphaguanidine, sulphathiazole, and sulphadiazine or (b) by

hydrolysing the 4-acetamidothiocarbanilide to 4-aminothiocarbanilide and subsequently allowing the resultant amine to react with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride, α -naphthalenesulphonyl chloride, β -naphthalenesulphonyl chloride, and benzyl chloride, or (c) by condensing phenyl isothiocyanate with *p*-chloroaniline and treating the resulting 4-chlorothiocarbanilide with γ -diethylamino-propyl^aamine, γ -piperidinopropyl^aamine, and γ -morpholinopropyl^aamine.

These thioureas have been characterised through their picrate in some cases.

EXPERIMENTAL

γ -Substituted Aminopropyl^aamines.— γ -Diethylamino-, γ -piperidino-, and γ -morpholinopropyl^aamines were obtained by following the method of Weisel and Yanki (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 725).

Reactions of Phenyl Isothiocyanate

(a) *With Primary Aliphatic Amines.*—A mixture of phenyl isothiocyanate (0.05*M*) and one of the above mentioned amines (0.05*M*) in 95% ethanol (25 c.c.) was refluxed on a water bath for 6 hours. Ethanol was distilled and the resulting syrupy mass was kept over calcium chloride in a desiccator for 48 hours. The crystals of the substituted thioureas separating were filtered, washed, and recrystallised from hot ethanol.

(b) *With Primary Aromatic Amines.*—Phenyl isothiocyanate (0.025*M*) was refluxed with aromatic amines (e.g., *p*-aminoacetanilide, *p*-aminoacetophenone or 3,5-dibromo-4-hydroxyaniline) (0.25*M*) in 95% ethanol (10 c.c.) for 15-20 minutes. The resulting thiourea derivatives were isolated as described above.

4-Chlorothiocarbanilide was prepared by the method of Kjellin (*Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 1076).

4-Ethoxycarbonylthiocarbanilide, reported earlier by Farooq and Hunter (*this Journal*, 1933, **10**, 465), was prepared by the above method in good yield.

4-Aminothiocarbanilide, already reported by Lellmann and Wurtheur (*Annalen*, 1885, **228**, 218) was obtained by hydrolysing 4-acetamidothiocarbanilide with 20% HCl and then neutralising it with 20% NaOH; yield 70%, m.p. 219.

The duration of reaction for amines like sulphanilamide, sulphaguanidine, sulphathiazole, sulphadiazine was, however, found to be 7 to 8 hours and a little more of solvent was required to facilitate the reaction.

Condensation of 4-Aminothiocarbanilide with Chloro Compounds.—A mixture of 4-aminothiocarbanilide (0.25*M*) and each (0.05*M*) of *p*-methylphenylsulphonyl chloride, α - and β -naphthalenesulphonyl chlorides or benzyl chloride, and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.25*M*) in ethanol (15 c.c.) was refluxed on a water bath for 7-8 hours in anhydrous condition. The substituted thioureas were extracted with hot ethanol and recrystallised from the same solvent (hot).

Condensation of 4-Chlorothiocarbanilide with Primary Aliphatic Amines.—A mixture of γ -diethylamino-, γ -piperidino-, or γ -morpholino-propyl^aamine (0.003*M*) and 4-chlorothiocarbanilide (0.003*M*) in ethanol (5 c.c.) was refluxed on a water bath for 4 to 5 hours in anhydrous condition. The resulting thioureas being very hygroscopic could not be crystallised. These were characterised by preparing their picrates.

TABLE I

Sl. No.	R	Thioureas.			Picrates.			%Nitrogen. Found, Calc.
		M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	
1.	CH ₃ CO.C ₆ H ₅ -	142°	80%	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ON ₂ S	..	..	..	..
2.	CH ₃ CO.NH.C ₆ H ₅ -	213°	95	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ON ₂ S	..	..	..	..
3.	HO.Br.C ₆ H ₄ -	168°	80	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ BrS	..	..	..	..
4.	C ₆ H ₅ .NH.Cl.S.HN.C ₆ H ₅ .SO ₃	116°	50	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	..	..	..	..
5.	.NH.SO ₃ .C ₆ H ₅ -	59°	55	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	..	..	..	..
6.	.NH.SO ₃ .C ₆ H ₅ -	83°	50	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	..	..	..	..
7.	C ₆ H ₅ NH.Cl.S.HN.C: (HN).NH.SO ₃ .C ₆ H ₅ -	65°	70	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	..	..	..	..
8.	Et ₃ :N.CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ .CH ₂ -	106°	40	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₂ S	..	..	..	..
9.	O .N.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .CH ₂ -	126°	30	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S	..	..	..	..
10.	.N.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .CH ₂ -	69°	35	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ S	..	..	..	..
11.	Et ₃ :N.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NH.C ₆ H ₅ -	..	..	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ S	156°	65%	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S	16.74 16.75
12.	O .N.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NH.C ₆ H ₅ -	..	..	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ON ₂ S	109°	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S	16.29 16.39
13.	.N.CH ₂ .CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NH.C ₆ H ₅ -	..	..	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ S	>300° (d)	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S	16.37 16.4° (d)
14.	α-C ₆ H ₇ .SO ₃ .HN.C ₆ H ₅ -	>300°	90	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	300°	50	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	13.22 13.3°
15.	β-C ₆ H ₇ .SO ₃ .HN.C ₆ H ₅ -	171°	85	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	300°	54	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	13.24 13.3°
16.	CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ .SO ₃ .HN.C ₆ H ₅ -	300°	85	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	300°	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	14.11 14.15
17.	C ₆ H ₅ .CH ₂ .NH.C ₆ H ₅ -	300°	90	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ S	300°	72	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S	14.90 14.97

An ethanolic solution of the resulting thiourea was heated on a water bath with an equal quantity of a saturated solution of picric acid in ethanol. On cooling, crystals of the respective picrates separated, which were recrystallised from hot ethanol.

The m.p., yields, and analytical data of the thioureas and their picrates obtained are recorded in Table I.

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